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MODERN APPROACHES TO INNOVATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract. In this article, the issues of educating the students of preschool educational organizations based on innovative ideas and preparing them for school are discussed.

Key words: education, regulatory document, educational effectiveness, multimedia technology, presentation, innovation.

INTRODUCTION

In Article 11 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education"¹:

“Preschool education aims to form a healthy and mature personality of a child, prepared for studying at school. This education is carried out in families, kindergartens and other educational institutions, regardless of the form of ownership, until the age of six or seven years.”

Preschool education documents state that preschool education is the first type of continuous education system and among the tasks necessary for the development of preschool education, it is necessary to search for and introduce effective psychological pedagogical methods of preschool education. It is also known that computerization and informatization of educational processes at all stages.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The evidence presented above is one of the urgent tasks of implementing innovative technologies in the educational process of preschool educational institutions, using multimedia tools during training, forming computer literacy of students, teaching them to use computers in an elementary way, and preparing them for school education. shows that

In a number of regulatory documents adopted in our republic, it is noted that the use of new innovative technologies, including multimedia technology, in the field of education is an urgent issue. Currently, multimedia-based electronic textbooks, manuals and various electronic didactic tools are being created and used in the field of education. However, the possibilities of using multimedia technology in the educational process of preschool educational institutions and implementing innovative methods in the course of training on this basis have not been sufficiently developed. The search, development and implementation of innovative technologies in preschool education, which is the first type of continuous education system, is an urgent task today.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

One of the innovative technologies of preschool educational institutions intended for use in the educational process is educational multimedia technology. Multimedia technology is one of the rapidly developing directions of modern information technology and consists of the following components: text, table, graphics, music, decoration, animation, audio, video. According to the

¹ The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" // Perfect generation is the foundation of Uzbekistan's development. - T.: "Sharq", 1998. - p. 20-29.

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author, the method of using multimedia technology and tools in education was called the "multimedia attack" method².

"Multimedia attack" method is used in the training part of teaching new material. The advantage of the "multimedia attack" method is as follows:

- multimedia didactic tool has an attractive, impressive, dynamic (dynamic state) effect;
- both hemispheres of the child's brain work simultaneously as a result of the presentation of educational material in a multimedia format;
- as a result of multimedia attack, children's attention stabilizes, their thinking increases, and learning materials are more acceptable;
- the activities of children in groups increase;
- a certain amount of time is saved due to the multimedia didactic tool interactive software product, the opportunity to provide additional information to the child is created due to the saved time.

In our opinion, multimedia technology for preschool children differs from traditional technologies in the following ways³:

- psychological aspects of children;
- children's age (6-7 years old);
- duration of computer training (15 minutes);
- suitability of the material for children (in the form of multimedia);
- volume of the material (intended for 30 minutes);
- level of complexity of the material (simple materials are chosen for children);
- their activity levels.

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions and suggestions can be made from the above:

- since preschool education is the first type of continuous education system, ensuring its integration with other types of education in the continuous education system;
- use of unique and appropriate multimedia technology for preschool education, development, creation of innovative technologies and formation of their methodology;
- using the computer not as a game tool, but as an educational tool, creating various educational and developmental computer games;
- one of the urgent tasks of the present day is to attract more information technologies, including multimedia technology, to scientific research works in preschool educational institutions. This is an innovative approach in the training process of preschool educational institutions.

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² Abdukadirov A.A., Begmatova N.Kh. Methodology of using multimedia technology in pre-school educational institutions (teaching manual). - Against: "Nasaf", 2011. - p. 163.

³ Begmatova N.Kh. Methodology for the implementation of computer educational games and school games. // Технологии и методики в образовании, Voronezh, 2011, No. 3. -p. 4.

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